

Behavioral Modification of Nigerian Youths against Illegal Migration through Purposeful Advertising

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ABSTRACT

International migration has become one of the most debated topics in many developed and developing countries. Migration—both voluntary and forced—is on the rise and has become a global phenomenon. People, especially youths whose hopes have increasingly become high are moving in larger numbers faster and further than at any other time in history due to incessant advertisement about easy got wealth, job and other basics necessities in developed countries. However, so many risks ranging from kidnapping, rape, trafficking to health complications and, in some cases, death have been associated with illegal migration. Meanwhile, Advertising has been recognized to be a powerful tool to influence the mind of the target audience. In view of this, the paper discussed how illegal migration could be discouraged using Advertising. Ameritest's Television Advertising Model was used to drive this discussion.

INTRODUCTION

Youths from low to middle socioeconomic classes are often the most vulnerable as they have a strong desire to travel abroad for further education or seek career opportunities (TNS, 2009). Human traffickers prey upon their dreams and aspiration for a better life and eventually trick them into forced labor or prostitution or some invariably lose their lives.

Meanwhile, studies have shown that people do not necessarily have a lack of information but have a mindset in which they express high tolerance for long periods of uncertainty in the trip overall, and seemingly optimistic estimates of how long the process might take and the risks involved. Such youths are said to comment that:

I am aware of the tough immigration laws passed these past couple of years and I am prepared for all consequences, as long as I reach Australia. I am sure my refugee claim will be approved by the Australian government and then I hope to live and start a family in a free country... (Farsight, 2016, p.13)

However, there is the general belief that if a customer is won, ten customers have been won. In other words, the use of Ameritest Television Model to discourage illegal migration becomes successful if at least some youths are being discouraged from taking such steps. IOM

(2003:69) said the dissemination of information is regarded as 'diminishing the capacity of traffickers and smugglers to exploit the limited knowledge of potential migrants and counterbalancing the false information provided by criminals involved in the facilitation of irregular migration.' This is consistent with a more recent report by the UN (2012: 6) which states that 'where migrants mugglers recruit migrants through misinformation about conditions of travel and the opportunities for remaining and working in a destination country awareness campaigns are crucial to counter such messages.'

EXISTING LITERATURE

Today, migration has become increasingly common as people move in search, as earlier noted, of security, education, employment and a better livelihood most especially between countries and continents (Loschmann & Siegel, 2014; Adikhari, 2013; de Haas, 2011b; Zimmerman, 2011). Even those that do not migrate are affected as relatives, friends or descendants of migrants or through experiences of change in their community as a result of departure of neighbors or arrival of newcomers. According to Castle (2000, p. 269) "Migration is often a result of economic and social development. This means that migration may contribute to education or health development and improved economic and social condition of

a migrant who is in search of better livelihood. It is said to erode the traditional boundaries between languages, cultures, ethnic groups and nation-states. It therefore challenges cultural traditions, national identity and political institutions and contributes to a decline in the autonomy of the nation-state. Therefore, a lot of people tend to move in search of better lives. However, with this mass move, migration is regarded to be problematic: something to be controlled and even curbed because it might bring about unpredictable changes to both their home countries and their destination countries as most people go to any extent to make their dreams of crossing the border come through.

In his opinion, Collier (2013, p. 6) said a veritable South–north ‘exodus’ is driven by poverty and income gaps, which threatens to spin out of control. Based on this common perception that poverty and income gaps are the ‘root causes’ of migration, countries that are considered ‘rich’ often adopt tighter border controls, which lead eventually to desperate people using illegal means to cross the borders. In response to such situations according to Castle (2000, p. 270), rich destination countries often seek to improve control as by dividing international migrants into categories as follows:

Temporary Labor Migrants also Known as Guest Workers or Overseas Contrary workers

Men and women who migrate for a limited period (from a few months to several years) in order to take up employment and send money home (remittances).

Highly Skilled and Business Migrants

People with qualification as managers, executives, professionals, technicians or similar, who move within the internal labor market of transnational co operations and international organisations, or who seek employment through international labor market for scarce skills. Many countries welcome such migrants and have special in "skilled and business migration" programmes to encourage them to come.

Irregular Migrants (Undocumented or Illegal Migrants)

People who enter a country usually in search of employment without the necessary or legal documents and permits (Vollmer, 2011). Many labor migration flows consist predominantly of undocumented migrants. In some cases, migration countries tacitly permit such migration since it allows mobilization of labor in response to employment demands without social cost or measure for protection of migrants.

Refugees

according to 1951 United Nations convention relating to the status of refugees, refugee is a person residing outside his or her country of nationality, who is unable or unwilling to return because of a 'well-founded fear of persecution on account of race, religion, nationality, membership in a particular social group or political opinion'. Others are: Asylum Seekers, Forced Migration family members and Return migrants.

From the above categorization it therefore, means that the choice to migrate by illegal could be made in the absence of legal route. Duvell (2009) explained that illegal border crossings are brought into being by a set of policy decisions and methods of border control that create categories of legal and illegal migrations and so, as a person passes through different countries, the migration category changes. This often results to long and risky journey.

Salaheddine (2010) corroborated the foregoing by stating that attempts to migrate illegally have always been dangerous, and he went further to give a similar scenario to what is occurring now in the Mediterranean Sea area, some post-WWII migrants in the Pyrenees perished in the snow trying to cross the mountains. There is therefore need to discourage youths especially from migrating by illegal route as the risks are much more than the benefits. This could be done, as this paper suggests, through Advertising.

ADVERTISING

Advertising is a paid, mediated form of communication from an identifiable source, designed to persuade the receiver to take some action, now or in the future (Richards & Curran, 2002: 74). ‘It is a form of communicative activation. It can be informative and persuasive in nature; utilizing the mass or new media to persuade the consumers to purchase goods and services. Advertising may be targeted at promoting a new product or designed to promote existing ones. Advertising, according to the British Institute of Practitioners in Advertising (IPA); presents the most persuasive message to the right prospects for the product or service at the lowest possible cost (Jefkins, 1992). It is ‘any form of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods and services usually paid for by an identified sponsor’ (Dominic, 2013). According to Benson-Eluwa, the advertising Practitioners of Nigeria (APCON) define advertising as an

information which is persuasive and informative about goods and services that paid for or sum of ideas which defined by advertisers via using media (Benson-Eluwa, 2004). On the other hand, Advertisement is an act of advertising which stands for giving public notice or to announcing publicly as a dictionary meaning (Tyagi and Kumar, 2004). When focused in the field of business and marketing, advertising is a propitious promotion of goods or services to the public, with the intention to draw attention of people and increase the amount of sales for these goods and services (Petley, 2003) Advertising plays an important role in everyday life of the audience. It mainly determines the image and way of life. It equally has an impact on the thinking and attitude of its audience and the world around them which invariably make it seen as a measure of the growth of civilization and a sign of the human race's strife for betterment and perfection. In the opinion of Frolova (2014, p.2) "Advertising shows us ready forms of behavior in a certain situation. It determines what is good and what is bad. We buy what people say or "advise". Little wonder the use of the various Advertising tools to encourage the audience about illegal migration.

Meanwhile Migration in itself is not evil. It is in fact, one of the great driving forces of human progress and development. People have moved all over the world for a variety of reasons ranging from economic factors (unemployment, rural poverty, unsustainable livelihood, job opportunities, better income and prospects for wealth creation, Industrial innovation and technical know-how for a new industry and pursuit of specialized education), Sociopolitical factors (family conflicts, ethnic, religious, racial and cultural parameters; warfare, or the threat of conflict), Political instability, Safety and security concerns (ethnic, religious, racial or cultural persecution) to infrastructure (including healthcare, education, utilities, transport and water) (PWC, 2017.p.24). Indeed, migration today has become one of the greatest byproducts of globalization. People, especially youths whose hopes have increasingly become high are moving in larger numbers faster and further than at any other time in history due to incessant advertisement about easy got wealth, job and other basics necessities in developed countries.

However, as promising and rewarding as international migration seems to be, the so many risks: kidnapping, rape, trafficking, health implications and, in some cases, death that have been associated with it when such movement is

said to be illegal is worrisome. Recently, studies and reports on the experience of Nigerian Youths in Libya have revealed that the reason for their arrests were usually 'illegal' entry or lack of migration documents such as identity documents or even health cards. Such arrests were typically accompanied by violence. The Libyan experience is one out of the numerous risks faced by Nigerian illegal immigrants who are predominantly youths. While the "profit-seeking exploiters" keep urging and mounting pressure on the youths via Advertising probably because it helps to influence attitude, perception, behaviors and values of audience (Jensen & Oster, 2009; Nash Pine & Messer2009; Byrd-Bredbenner, 2000), it becomes urgent and compelling f to invent a model to reverse the situation. In view of this, the paper is proposing the same promotional tool which the enticers and exploiters have employed to mislead the youths in order to discourage illegal migration using Ameritest's Television Advertising Model. Psychologists have analyzed Advertising to occupy the central position of motivations of recipients. This is because of their influence on the perception of its audience (Mittelstaedt, 1990) as it seeks to reduce the complexity of an issue by presenting it in an easy-to-understand, interpretive package. According to Calfee (1998), there are evidences that advertisements do educate and bring awareness to the public on certain issues like illegal migration. As a result of this, the paper is proposing good easy – to - understand communication with Ameritest Heuristic Television Advertising Model.

This is a teaching model by Charles Young. The purpose of the model is to focus attention on learning how and why an ad is working, with the goal of improving understanding and aiding judgment. The model organizes all the questions asked by earlier theories in order to provide us with a complete picture of how to fit together all the different dimensions of performance that modern ad researchers usually attempt to measure. In the model, information is arranged in a hierarchy and at the top is what pre-testing is supposed to predict: in-market results. In the case, the in-market result is the change of attitude towards illegal migration.

EXECUTION AND PROMISE

Essentially, the model says that for any commercial to be effective it must accomplish three things, namely:

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- It must get noticed and attract an audience.
- The audience must know who is sending the advertising message.
- Once the commercial has the audience's attention; it must "sell" them something—drive sales in the short run or at least create a positive predisposition for sales in the long run.

Ameritest Heuristic Television Advertising Model

Source: Young, 2008 p. 39

By implication, for any advertisement on illegal migration to be effective, it must be noticed by attracting the target audience and such audience must be able to know and understand the message. According to Mueller, (1991.p28) execution concentrates on “how it is said”. This means that there is advertising strategy adopted for a specific purpose which thus guides the execution. Porter (1998) defined strategy as doing same thing in a different manner. Applying this, Eger (1987) while examining global TV advertising and revealed that the theme commonly remained the same but execution varied from one country to another. He therefore, proposed that differences in execution could be designed to reflect the culture of a given market. It is thus inferred that the various elements of execution ranging from picture selection, size, color, general layout, captioning, and use of text used by Television advertisement, Social media, radio, and other traditional media should be done differently while maintaining the theme in order to have one voice. Advertisements on illegal migration could focus on the negative aspects of this type of migration. This is aimed at deterring migrants from leaving.

In contrast, analysis of execution formats. Eger (1987) revealed a variety of factors and how they were used in various countries. For

example, story, fantasy and joke were mostly used in the U.K. sample whereas slice of life, problem and solution, product comparison, ordinary person, use of children, voice over and music were dominant in the Czech sample. Even though Nigeria has been reported to have more than 250 tribes with different culture, upholding honesty and family heritage and history values run across board. Meanwhile Pécoud, (2010) suggested that

Understanding the decisions to leave is therefore a key part of success. The assumption is that a lack of accurate information generates irrational and risky irregular migration behaviors ... If migrants were informed of the proper conditions of entry, they would be deterred from unlawful migration (Pécoud, 2010, p. 196).

To get the attention of the audience, the Ad needs to identify with the reasons or decisions to leave shore of the country. Another copy of the Ad show the where a trusted relations who might be relatives, friends, neighbors, work colleagues is giving knowledge or stories of hope and success transmitted a known migrant. Another cast overhears and try as much as possible to discourage by vividly sharing her story at Libya as people with their beliefs and understandings (and ultimately behavior) are more likely influenced by trusted network.

This is not trying to stop migration, but rather to inform audience about the risks and dangers associated with such type of migration.

VERBAL AND VISUAL DIAGNOSTICS

The execution of a TV and video clip for social media advertisement contains visual aspects, such as size, material, and colour (Horstmann, 2011; Horstmann, 2005). Therefore, advertising explicitly uses unexpected visual aspects to trigger a surprise effect (Himpe, 2008). Choice of words used should portray the feelings and thoughts of the target audience and visual should also relate with the visual representations that best match their feelings.

CONTENT, FORM AND FOCUS

Contents, forms and focus of illegal migration advertisements should be in line with the culture, environment and undocumented life in the home country of the illegal migrants. Focus should be more on the risks and dangers concerning the journey itself, pointing out the potential life-threatening situations at sea or in the desert, and the ruthlessness of smugglers. Other advertisements should also warn migrants about the risk of falling into the hands of human traffickers. The Swiss government, for example, funded a commercial which was shown on television in Cameroon and Nigeria. In the commercial, an African migrant phones his father from somewhere in Europe in the pouring rain and assures him that all is well and that he is attending university, while in reality he is living on the street, being chased by the police and having to beg for a living.

The warning shown on the screen should be: 'don't believe everything you hear; Leaving is not always living.' In this campaign and numerous similar campaigns, a rather dark representation of migration underlies the messages sent to potential migrants leaving one's country systematically leads to failure, misfortune and exploitation (Pécoud, 2010; Heller, 2014). Other examples can be: 'You cannot outrun your shadow! How long can you be on the lookout? [...] you risk being sent back home very swiftly...The only way is the legal way.'

According to Nieuwenhuys and Pécoud, (2007, p.23) Information campaigns have been deemed essential in fighting trafficking and smuggling, as they reduce the vulnerability of potential victims by raising awareness regarding the risk of being caught in criminal networks.

COMMUNICATION, FIT, DRAMA AND FLOW OF EMOTION

Emotion is defined as a condition of the mind that arises from cognitive assessments of events or thoughts; comes with physiological experiences; is often associated with actions, such as gestures and facial movements; and may result in actions to manage the emotions (Bagozzi, Gopinath, & Nyer, 1999). Emotional reactions and the unconscious are important when painting a full picture of people's interpretations of stimuli (Wyer, Adaval & Colcombe 2002; Zwaan & Radvansky, 1998).

Meanwhile, conditions of the illegal migrants when caught have frequently been described as deplorable. Men and women were usually kept separately but unaccompanied boys were often detained with unknown adult males. Beatings and violence were commonplace and sexual violence by guards, an ongoing risk for female detainees. There were typically no rooms for complaint. Food was usually inadequate; most said they only received one meagre meal a day. Sanitation conditions were deplorable; toilets were filthy and insufficient in number, and access to showers and a change of clothing, rare. Most reported sleeping in crowded cells without bedding or mattresses. Outdoor access was restricted except in situations where detainees were taken out to do unpaid work for detention centre staff or outside employers. Worst still, medical treatment was usually lacking.

Spontaneous inferences from these 'testimonies' fit together in the advertisements employed in such a way that people would construct and comprehend the situation (Wyer et al., 2002). Such testimonies can be both meta-linguistic (verbal) and "image" (nonverbal) components. According to Wyer and his colleagues, while the image component of an episode model in the brain is obligatory, the verbal component is optional. Hence, people may not always be able to readily verbalize their impression of an event, so verbal measures are insufficient to produce the full picture of audience's spontaneous impression. As a result there is need to include the two forms of communication in any form of the employed drama of an Advertisement might.

According to Awodiya (1995) "...to use the weapon we have; our pen, our zeal and eloquence to awaken in our people the song of liberation with our writings" p.33. We wash away the stigma of inferiority, rouse our dormant energies, unmask the pest and traitors among us, and preach the positive sermons. This indeed is

the power of playwrights who are part of the society and so, have a better explanation of what is happening around them as they operate as the conscience of the society. They are said to be committed towards restoring order to the communities which have been engulfed in a myriad of socio-political and economic disorder. Therefore, emotional experiences of the returnees should be co-created, and advertising planning should link the “illegal story” with target audience’s “life story.”

CONCLUSION

Youths from low to middle socioeconomic classes are often the most vulnerable as they have a strong desire to travel abroad for further education or seek career opportunities (TNS, 2009). Human traffickers prey upon their dreams and aspiration for a better life and eventually trick them into forced labor or prostitution or some invariably lose their lives.

Meanwhile, studies have shown that people do not necessarily have a lack of information but have a mindset in which they express high tolerance for long periods of uncertainty in the trip overall, and seemingly optimistic estimates of how long the process might take and the risks involved. However, there is the general belief that if a customer is won, ten customers have been won. In This paper, the possibility of employing the use of Ameritest Television Model to discourage illegal migration becomes a prospective successful tool towards a possible modification of behavior and attitude of the Nigerian youths to illegal migration have been discussed. It provides all the features of the advertisement in order to achieve the desired result.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adikhari, P. (2013). Conflict-Induced Displacement, Understanding the Causes of Flight. *Am. J. Polit. Sci.* 57, 82–89. doi: 10.1111/j.1540-5907.2012.00598.x
- [2] Awodiya, M. P (1995). *The Drama of Femi Osofisan: A Critical Perspective*. Ibadan: Kraft Books Ltd;
- [3] Byrd-Bredbenner, C. (2002). Saturday morning children's television advertising. A longitudinal content analysis. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 30, 382-403
- [4] Bagozzi, R. P., Gopinath, M., & Nyer, P. U. (1999). The role of emotions in marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 27, (2), 184-206.
- [5] Calfee, J. (1998). How Advertising informs to our Benefits. *Consumer Research*. pp 115 – 129
- [6] Duvell, F., 2009. Comparative Policy Brief - Pathways and policies, *PATHWAYS INTO IRREGULARITY: The Social Construction of Irregular Migration*. European Commission.
- [7] De Haas, H., 2011b. Mediterranean migration futures: Patterns, drivers and scenarios. *Glob. Environ. Change* 21, S59–S69. Doi:10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.09.003
- [8] Eger, J.M. (1987) *Global Television: An Executive Overview*. Columbia Journal of World Business. 5-10
- [9] Frolova, S. (2014). “The Role of Advertising in Promoting a Product”. An unpublished Thesis at Centria University of Applied Sciences
- [10] Heller, C. (2014). Perception management–Detering potential migrants through information campaigns. *Global Media and Communication*, 10(3),303-318. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177 /1742766514552355>
- [11] Jensen, R., & Oster, E. (2009). The power of TV: Cable television and Women's status in India. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 143, 1057-1094
- [12] Loschmann, C., Siegel, M., (2014). The influence of vulnerability on migration intentions in Afghanistan. *Migr. Dev.* 3, 142–162. doi:10.1080/21632324.2014.885259
- [13] Mittelstaedt R.A. (1990), Economics, Psychology, and the Literature of the Sub discipline of Consumer Behavior, *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 18, 4.
- [14] Mueller, B. (1991) “An Analysis of Information Content in Standardized vs. Specialized Multinational Advertisements,” *Journal of International Business Studies*. 23-39
- [15] Nash, A., Pine, K.J., & Messer, D.J. (2009). Television alcohol advertising. Do children really mean what they say? *British Journal of Development Psychology*, 27, 85-104
- [16] Pécoud, A. (2010). ‘Informing Migrants to Manage Migration? An Analysis of IOM's Information Campaigns’. In M. Geiger & A. Pécoud (Eds.) *the Politics of International Migration Management*. Palgrave Macmillan. Accessed 9th September, 2018. Retried from: <http://www.freelists.org/archives/colombiamigra/062013/pdf4LDT5DyS9G.pdf#page=194>
- [17] Salaheddine, R. (2010). *Illegal Immigration: Causes, Consequences, And National Security Implications? A project thesis at the Army War College, Carlisle Barracks, USA*
- [18] Vollmer, B.,(2011). *Irregular Migration in the UK, Definitions, Pathways and Scale*. *Migr. Obs. Univ. Oxf.*
- [19] Wyer, R. S., R. Adaval, and S. J. Colcombe. (2002) “Narrative-Based Representations of Social Knowledge: Their Construction and Use in Comprehension, Memory and Judgment.”

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- [19] In *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, vol. 35, M. P. Zanna, ed. San Diego: Academic Press, Young, C.E (2008). *Advertising Research Handbook*. Washington: Ideas in Flight
- [20] Zimmerman, S., (2011). Danger, Loss, and Disruption in Somalia after 1991: Practicalities and Needs Behind Refugee Decision-Making. *Refug. Surv. Q.* 30, 45–66. doi: 10.1093 /rsq /hdr004
- [21] Zwaan, R. A., and G. A. Radvansky. (1998) Situation Models in Language Comprehension and Memory. *Psychological Bulletin* 123(2), 162–185.

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